

DEVELOPMENT FOR SMALL BUSINESS IN MAHALLAS

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Mahallas are community groups that have existed for centuries in Uzbek culture. In every community of our people there is a group of elders who are expected to help solve any social problems and conflicts that arise in the community. Although mahallas are not religious organizations, they promote traditional Islamic ideas about social roles and behavior. They help organize weddings, funerals and circumcisions - the main events in the life of the people. They also try to prevent divorces (married couples must appear before the mahalla before legal divorce proceedings begin), the mahalla must also ensure that the elderly are taken care of, and criminals are punished (criminals may be forced to leave the mahalla) [3,42].

The Uzbek makhalla committee organizes various forms of public works. For example, the mahalla organizes the cleaning of streets from garbage and supervises operations to clean irrigation canals. Another important function of the mahalla is the organization of "hashara". This is a traditional Uzbek way of mutual assistance, when community members form a group that helps one or another family build a house or harvest a crop. The most important thing from the point of view of social assistance is that the mahalla traditionally provides care for the elderly residents and children of the community.

There are about 14 thousand makhalla committees in the country, the number of families in them varies from 150 to 5.5 thousand. Mahallas were not closed during the Soviet period, but their activities were not encouraged. Since 1992, they have been officially supported by state authorities and given administrative responsibilities. Chairmen and secretaries of mahalla committees, in which there are more than 500 families, now receive salaries from local authorities (khokimiyats). The chairman is elected by the community, but candidates must be approved by the local district khokim.

Development for small businesses in the mahallas (neighborhoods or local communities) of Uzbekistan is a crucial aspect of the country's economic and social progress. Here's an overview of the key elements involved in fostering small business development in these areas:

1. Government Support and Policies

Incentives and Grants: The Uzbek government has been providing various incentives, including tax breaks, low-interest loans, and grants to encourage entrepreneurship in mahallas.

Simplified Registration: Efforts have been made to simplify the process of registering a small business, reducing bureaucracy, and making it easier for locals to start their ventures.

Training and Development Programs: Government agencies and NGOs often organize workshops and training sessions to equip local entrepreneurs with essential business skills.

2. Access to Finance

Microfinance Institutions: These play a vital role in providing small loans to entrepreneurs who may not have access to traditional banking services.

Credit Unions: Locally operated credit unions are often more accessible to the residents of mahallas, providing loans tailored to their needs.

Government-Backed Funds: Special funds have been established to support the development of small businesses, especially those led by women and young people.

3. Infrastructure Development

Improving Local Infrastructure: Enhancing road networks, telecommunications, and electricity supply in mahallas can significantly impact the growth of small businesses.

Marketplaces and Trade Centers: Developing local markets and trade centers within mahallas can provide business owners with direct access to consumers.

4. Community Engagement and Social Capital

Mahalla Committees: These local governance bodies play a significant role in supporting small businesses by facilitating connections, offering advice, and sometimes even providing financial support.

Cooperatives: Encouraging the formation of cooperatives allows small business owners to pool resources, share risks, and increase their market reach.

5. Digitalization and Innovation

E-commerce Platforms: Expanding access to digital marketplaces allows small businesses in mahallas to reach a broader audience.

Digital Skills Training: Providing training in digital literacy and online business management helps entrepreneurs modernize their operations.

6. Challenges

Access to Markets: Small businesses in mahallas often struggle to access broader markets, limiting their growth potential.

Financial Literacy: A lack of financial literacy can hinder the ability of entrepreneurs to manage their finances effectively.

Regulatory Challenges: Despite improvements, navigating regulatory requirements can still be a hurdle for many small businesses.

7. Success Stories

Highlighting successful businesses that have grown from mahallas can inspire others and provide models for replication.

8. Future Prospects

Sustainability Initiatives: Encouraging sustainable business practices, such as eco-friendly production methods, can open up new opportunities.

Youth and Women Entrepreneurship: Continued focus on empowering youth and women through targeted programs can drive further development in the mahallas.

The development of small businesses in Uzbekistan's mahallas is essential for local economic growth, reducing poverty, and fostering community resilience. With ongoing support and targeted interventions, these businesses can thrive and contribute significantly to the country's overall development.

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